

Biomimetic Approach towards Filbertone

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Abstract

Within this study, we would like to present a different approach from commercially available natural starting materials towards filbertone. In a three step procedure, combining Aldol chemistry and fermentation, we are able to realize this reaction without using any inorganic reagents or catalysts. The required stereochemistry should be introduced during the fermentative reduction of (*E*)-3-methylpent-3-en-2-one employing commercially available baker's yeast. This reaction could be accomplished in good yield and, provided access to the enantiomerically enriched intermediate (3*S*)-3-methylpentan-2-one. The obtained enantiomeric excess of 70 % *ee* correlates very well with the observed value of filbertone isolated from raw hazelnuts. Unfortunately, the reaction conditions of the second acid catalysed Aldol condensation to furnish filbertone proved to be too harsh to preserve the installed stereocenter and resulted in complete racemization of the obtained filbertone.

Keywords: filbertone, fermentation, Aldol condensation, enantiomeric excess

Introduction

Since its first publication as flavour material in 1985 [1] and subsequent identification in raw and roasted hazelnuts in 1989 [2] filbertone (**5**) is known as the character impact compound in hazelnuts and has been extensively studied during the last decades [3]. Whereas the enantiomeric excess of the (*S*)-enantiomer in raw hazelnuts is found to be quite constant around 70 % *ee*, it drops remarkably during roasting. Considering the observed increase of the total amount of filbertone during roasting, this could be attributed to a release of racemic material from a precursor. Alternatively, partial racemization while heating has also been observed, depending on the matrix [4]. Despite the obvious tendency for racemization, the detected enantiomeric excess is used as one potential marker to identify adulteration in hazelnut products [5].

The general trend towards natural and sustainable flavours poses an enormous task for the industry, especially in the case of filbertone (**5**), as the commercial isolation from hazelnuts is hardly viable due to the low amounts present. Several routes to filbertone (**5**) are described in the literature; however they still require inorganic reagents and catalysts. In addition, the so far described approaches towards enantiomerically enriched filbertone are all relying on starting materials from the chiral pool [3, 6].

Experimental

The baker's yeast used for these experiments was purchased from UNIFERM GMBH & CO. KG, all other chemicals and solvents were obtained from MERCK KGAA. Optical rotation was measured on a UniPol 1000 (SCHMIDT & HAENSCH), chiral GC experiments were carried out on an Agilent GC 7890 system employing a Hydrodex- β -TBDAC column (25 m, 0.25 mm i.d.). The conditions for the analysis were: split injection (split ratio 1:50), injector temperature 60 °C – 12 °C/sec – 220 °C; oven temperature 40 °C – 2 °C/min – 180 °C. Hydrogen was used as the carrier gas and the flow rate was 2.0 mL/min.

(*E*)-3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**)

30.0 g (1.0 eq.) of 2-butanone (**1**) was treated under stirring with 15.0 g water, 60.6 g (1.0 eq.) of tartaric acid and subsequently with 33.8 mL (1.5 eq.) of acetaldehyde (**2**). The resulting reaction mixture was heated to 120 °C for 16 h in a closed autoclave, which resulted in an inherent pressure of 6 bar. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and washed with water and NaOH solution (5%) to remove the acid. The product was extracted with 200 mL methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE). Finally, the organic phase was concentrated under reduced pressure and the obtained product was distilled (at 30 mbar, at 90 °C) to give 21.6 g of (*E*)-3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**). The analytical data was comparable to that found in literature [7]. Yield: 55 %.

3-methylpentan-2-one (**4**)

To a baker's yeast solution (750 mL of a 200 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), containing 235 g/L yeast) 1.5 g of (*E*)-3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**) were added. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was steam distilled at 120 °C under normal pressure.

The resulting water-product mixture was extracted with MTBE. After removal of the solvent, the product was distilled under reduced pressure (at 400 mbar, at 80 °C) to give 0.56 g of 3-methylpentan-2-one (**4**). $[\alpha]_D^{26} = 8.0^\circ$, ($c = 0.18$ g/L, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$); literature: $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +8.0^\circ$ ($c = 1.0$, CHCl_3); 70 % *ee* in favour of the (*S*)-enantiomer. Other analytical data was comparable to that found in literature [7] as well. Yield: 37 %.

Filbertone

20.0 g (1.0 eq) of 3-methylpentan-2-one (**4**) was treated under stirring with 19.2 g (0.5 eq) of citric acid and subsequently with 16.9 ml (1.5 eq) of acetaldehyde. The resulting reaction mixture was then heated to 120 °C for 10 h in an autoclave. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and treated with 19.2 g (0.5 eq) of citric acid and subsequently with 16.9 ml (1.5 eq) of acetaldehyde. The resulting reaction mixture was then heated to 120 °C for another 15 h in an autoclave. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and washed with water and a 10 % KOH solution to remove the organic acid. The product was extracted with 400 mL MTBE. Finally, the organic phase was concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting product was distilled under reduced pressure (at 10 mbar, at 90 °C) to give 2.77 g of filbertone (**5**). The analytical data was comparable to those found in literature [2]. Yield: 11 %.

Results and discussion

Inspired by the synthetic strategy chosen by Cheng [8], we envisaged to employ only sustainable organic starting materials and reagents to furnish the first truly green and enantioselective synthesis of filbertone not relying on starting materials from the chiral pool.

Acid catalysed Aldol reaction to (*E*)-3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**)

Figure 1: Aldol Reaction of 2-butanone (**2**).

In a first step – the condensation reaction of acetaldehyde (**1**) and butanone (**2**) – the hydrochloric acid could be replaced by tartaric acid without observing a significant drop in yield (Figure 1). Due to the high volatility the reaction is conducted in a stainless steel autoclave at an inherent pressure of 6 bar. The reaction also proceeds employing other natural acids like formic acid or citric acid, however, the yield drops dramatically.

Fermentation employing Baker's Yeast

The subsequent reduction of 3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**) should be achieved by replacing the palladium catalyst by commercially available baker's yeast (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Reduction of 3-methylpent-3-en-2-one (**3**).

As the consumer is very conscious about the use of genetically modified organisms for the production of flavourings, the use of traditional baker's yeast can be regarded as favourable. However, due to the low conversion rate towards the used substrate, the concentration of the yeast is very high, which adds additional complexity to the downstream processing, especially as the product is highly volatile. It is expected, that the isolated yield of the 3-methylpentan-2-one (**4**) could be improved further by adapting the isolation and purification conditions. The configuration of the newly generated stereocenter was determined as (*S*) *via* comparison of the optical rotation to the existing literature [7]. The enantiomeric excess was determined as 70 % *ee* *via* chiral GC analysis, which correlates very well with the observed value of filbertone isolated from raw hazelnuts.

Acid catalysed Aldol reaction to Filbertone

In the final step, Cheng used zinc acetate which could be again replaced by natural organic acids with good selectivity albeit obtaining only low conversion (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Acid catalysed Aldol reaction to filbertone.

Interestingly, citric acid instead of tartaric acid proved to be especially beneficial for this transformation, which has to be carried out in a stainless steel autoclave due to the high volatility for the reagents which resulted in an inherent pressure of 6 bars. A larger excess of citric acid and acetic aldehyde (1) and a prolonged reaction time are necessary compared to the first aldol reaction, due to the lower reactivity of the 3-methylpentan-2-one (4) in this reaction. Albeit the yield of 11 % is rather poor, the reaction is quite selective, as 70 % of the starting material could be re-isolated, which results in a conversion-adjusted yield of 37 %. Unfortunately, the reaction conditions are too harsh to preserve the parent stereocenter and the starting material undergoes complete racemization which consequently leads to racemic filbertone (5) as well.

Conclusion

Filbertone (5) was generated in a three step procedure by using only natural and sustainable raw materials, reagents and processes. The reduction employing non-genetically modified baker's yeast furnished an enantiomerically enriched intermediate. Unfortunately, complete racemization occurs during the final step, which again underlines tendency of filbertone to racemise under various conditions.

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